

Joint Hybrid/Passive Beamforming Design in IRS-aided Multi-User MISO Systems for PS-SWIPT

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Abstract—This paper considers an intelligent reflecting surface (IRS)-aided multiple-input single-output broadcasting system for power-splitting (PS) simultaneous wireless information and power transfer, where the access point adopts an analog/digital architecture. We aim at jointly optimizing the hybrid precoder, passive beamformer (PB), and PS ratios, such that the transmit sum-power is minimized subject to the quality-of-service requirements of the receivers. We develop a two-layer, penalty-based block coordinate descent algorithm to solve this challenging non-convex optimization problem and employ manifold optimization to update the analog precoding weights and IRS phase shifts. We also derive a low-complexity, decoupled iterative design where the analog precoder is updated via the stochastic gradient descent algorithm and the PB is computed via the successive convex approximation method. Numerical simulations highlight the performance gains of the proposed schemes over various benchmarks and shed light on the impact of the parameter settings on the performance.

Index Terms—Simultaneous wireless information and power transfer, hybrid precoding, intelligent reflecting surface, manifold optimization, stochastic optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-user multiple-input single-output (MISO) technology is often utilized in simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) systems to enhance both the data and energy rate via transmit precoding [1]. Nevertheless, the stringent cost and energy consumption constraints of the access points (AP) in Internet-of-Things (IoT) setups limit the number of antennas, and the corresponding performance gains, under a fully-digital (FD) implementation.

The adoption of an analog/digital (A/D) architecture, which combines a digital baseband precoder (DBP) with an analog radio frequency precoder (RFP) that is commonly realized via a network of phase shifters, has been considered in the literature as a workaround to this problem [2], [3]. This implementation utilizes fewer RF chains than antennas. Intelligent reflecting surface (IRS) is an emerging technology that further boosts the performance in a cost-effective and energy-efficient manner via a passive (reflect) beamformer (PB) [4].

However, prior studies on joint or decoupled HP/PB optimization for IRS-assisted MISO broadcasting systems have

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considered scenarios with millimeter-wave (mmWave) channels [5] or massive MISO setups [6], which limit the applicability of the derived schemes. Likewise, the work [7], which considers secure mmWave SWIPT, assumes separate information decoding (ID) and energy harvesting (EH) receivers and focuses on a decoupled design with a codebook-based RFP.

This paper considers instead a more general power-splitting (PS)-SWIPT setup. Furthermore, *it represents the first study, to the best of our knowledge, on the joint HP/PB /PS ratios optimization for SWIPT*. Specifically, we aim at minimizing the transmit sum-power under the quality-of-service (QoS) requirements of the users. In order to tackle this non-convex optimization problem, we develop a two-layer, penalty-based block coordinate descent (BCD) algorithm. The RFP and PB are updated via the Riemannian conjugate gradient (RCG) algorithm. We also derive a low-complexity, decoupled iterative design, where the RFP is updated via the stochastic gradient descent (SGD) algorithm under the alternating minimization (AM) framework, whereas the PB is computed via the successive convex approximation (SCA) method. Note that *the derived schemes do not require channel sparsity or excessive number of AP antennas*. Numerical simulations highlight the performance gains of the proposed schemes over various benchmarks and provide insights regarding the impact of the parameter settings on the performance.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The considered system consists of a set $\mathcal{K} \triangleq \{1, \dots, K\}$ of single-antenna PS-SWIPT receivers, an AP with a set $\mathcal{M} \triangleq \{1, \dots, M\}$ of antennas and a set $\mathcal{L} \triangleq \{1, \dots, L\}$ of RF chains ($K \leq L < M$) that adopts the fully-connected A/D structure, and an IRS with a set $\mathcal{N} \triangleq \{1, \dots, N\}$ of passive reflecting elements, as shown in Fig. 1.

We assume a quasi-static, flat fading channel model. The direct AP–user k , reflecting IRS–user k , and incident AP–IRS baseband equivalent channels are denoted by $\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^M$, $\mathbf{h}_{r,k}^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^N$, and $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$, respectively, $\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$, where $(\cdot)^\dagger$ represents the conjugate transpose operation. Let $\Theta \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ and $\theta \in \mathbb{C}^N$ be the passive beamforming matrix and vector, which are defined as $\Theta \triangleq \text{diag}(e^{j\theta_1}, \dots, e^{j\theta_N})$ and $\theta \triangleq \text{diag}(\Theta^*)$, respectively, with $\theta_n \in [0, 2\pi)$ representing the phase shift of the n -th IRS element, $\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$. Then, the IRS-cascaded and the effective AP–user k channel, $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ and $\mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^M$, are defined as $\mathbf{H}_k \triangleq \text{diag}(\mathbf{h}_{r,k}^\dagger) \mathbf{H}$ and $\mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \triangleq \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger + \mathbf{h}_{r,k}^\dagger \Theta \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger + \theta^\dagger \mathbf{H}_k$, respectively.

Fig. 1. System setup, fully-connected A/D AP, and PS-SWIPT receiver.

The transmitted signal $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is written as $\mathbf{x} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_k s_k$, where $\mathbf{F}_R \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times L}$ represents the RFP, $\mathbf{f}_k \in \mathbb{C}^L$ denotes the digital precoding vector assigned to user k , and $s_k \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ is the data symbol intended for that user. Under a fully-connected structure, $\mathbf{F}_R(m, l) = e^{j\varphi_{m,l}}$, where $\varphi_{m,l} \in [0, 2\pi)$, $\forall m \in \mathcal{M}, \forall l \in \mathcal{L}$. The transmit sum-power is expressed as $P_S = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_k\|^2$.

The signal-to-interference-plus-noise-ratio (SINR) at the ID branch of user k is given by

$$\text{SINR}_k = \frac{|\mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_k|^2}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} |\mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j|^2 + \sigma_k^2 + \frac{\sigma_{c,k}^2}{\rho_k}}, \quad (1)$$

where σ_k^2 and $\sigma_{c,k}^2$ denote the power of the receiver noise n_k and baseband conversion noise ν_k , respectively (see Fig. 1), whereas $\rho_k \in [0, 1]$ stands for the PS ratio. The received RF power at the EH branch of that user, ignoring the negligible noise power, is expressed as $E_k = (1 - \rho_k) \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} |\mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j|^2$. The harvested direct current (DC) power at the output of the EH unit is given by $E_{H,k} = F(E_k)$, where $F(\cdot)$ is a monotonically increasing, non-linear EH function.

The SINR and EH constraints of user k are expressed as $\text{SINR}_k \geq \gamma_k$ and $E_{H,k} \geq \tilde{Q}_k \Leftrightarrow E_k \geq F^{-1}(\tilde{Q}_k) \triangleq Q_k$, where $\gamma_k > 0$, $\tilde{Q}_k > 0$, and $Q_k > 0$ denote the minimum SINR, harvested power, and received RF power target.

III. JOINT HYBRID/PASSIVE BEAMFORMING AND RECEIVE POWER SPLITTING DESIGN

The optimization problem of interest is formulated as:

$$(P1): \min_{\mathbf{F}_R, \{\mathbf{f}_k\}, \Theta, \{\rho_k\}} P_S \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{s.t. C1: } \text{SINR}_k \geq \gamma_k, \text{ C2: } E_k \geq Q_k, \quad (2b)$$

$$\text{C3: } |\Theta(n, n)| = 1, \text{ C4: } |\mathbf{F}_R(m, l)| = 1, \quad (2c)$$

$$\text{C5: } 0 \leq \rho_k \leq 1. \quad (2d)$$

(P1) is a non-convex optimization problem due to the coupling of the optimization variables in the QoS constraints C1 and C2 and the non-convex unit modulus constraints C3 and C4.

A. Problem Reformulation

Let $\mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j \triangleq t_{k,j}, \forall k, j \in \mathcal{K}$. We convert these equality constraints into a quadratic function and add it as a penalty term in the objective function of problem (P1). We also substitute $t_{k,j}$ in the QoS constraints to decouple the optimization variables, thus yielding:

$$(P2): \min_{\mathbf{F}_R, \{\mathbf{f}_k\}, \Theta, \{\rho_k\}, \{t_{k,j}\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_k\|^2 + \frac{1}{2\delta} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j - t_{k,j} \right|^2 \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{s.t. C6: } \frac{|t_{k,k}|^2}{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} |t_{k,j}|^2 + \sigma_k^2 + \frac{\sigma_{c,k}^2}{\rho_k}} \geq \gamma_k, \quad (3b)$$

$$\text{C7: } (1 - \rho_k) \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} |t_{k,j}|^2 \geq Q_k, \text{ C8: C3-C5}, \quad (3c)$$

where $\delta > 0$ denotes a coefficient that penalizes the violations of the equality constraints. Next, we divide the optimization variables into four blocks and apply the BCD method.

B. Inner-Layer of the Penalty-Based BCD Algorithm

1) *Optimizing $\{\mathbf{f}_k\}$* : With all blocks fixed except $\{\mathbf{f}_k\}$, problem (P2) is reduced to:

$$(P3): \min_{\{\mathbf{f}_k\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_k\|^2 + \frac{1}{2\delta} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j - t_{k,j} \right|^2. \quad (4)$$

(P3) is a convex unconstrained quadratic minimization problem. Based on the first-order optimality condition, we obtain:

$$\mathbf{f}_k^* = \frac{1}{2\delta} \mathbf{A}^{-1} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger t_{j,k}, \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k \in \mathbb{C}^L$ and $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times L}$ are defined as $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}_k^\dagger \triangleq \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R$ and $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}_L + \frac{1}{2\delta} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_j \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_j^\dagger$, respectively.

2) *Optimizing \mathbf{F}_R* : With all blocks fixed except \mathbf{F}_R , problem (P2) is reduced to:

$$(P4): \min_{\mathbf{F}_R} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_k\|^2 + \frac{1}{2\delta} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j - t_{k,j} \right|^2 \text{ s.t. C4}. \quad (6)$$

Let us define $\mathbf{F}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times ML}$, $\mathbf{f} \in \mathbb{C}^{ML}$, and $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j}^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}^{ML}$ as $\mathbf{F}_k \triangleq \mathbf{f}_k^\dagger \otimes \mathbf{I}_M$, $\mathbf{f} \triangleq \text{vec}(\mathbf{F}_R)$, and $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j}^\dagger \triangleq \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_j$, respectively, where \otimes stands for the Kronecker product. Then, $\mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_k = (\mathbf{f}_k^\dagger \otimes \mathbf{I}_M) \text{vec}(\mathbf{F}_R) = \mathbf{F}_k \mathbf{f}$ and $\mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_j \mathbf{f} = \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j}^\dagger \mathbf{f}$. Thus, we can rewrite problem (P4) as:

$$(P5): \min_{\mathbf{f}} f(\mathbf{f}) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \|\mathbf{F}_k \mathbf{f}\|^2 + \frac{1}{2\delta} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j}^\dagger \mathbf{f} - t_{k,j} \right|^2 \quad (7a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } |\mathbf{f}(q)| = 1, q \in \mathcal{Q} \triangleq \{1, \dots, ML\}. \quad (7b)$$

Note that the Euclidean gradient of $f(\mathbf{f})$ over \mathbf{f} is given by:

$$\nabla f(\mathbf{f}) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \frac{\mathbf{F}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_k \mathbf{f}}{\|\mathbf{F}_k \mathbf{f}\|} + \frac{1}{\delta} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j}^\dagger (\mathbf{f}^\dagger \hat{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j} - t_{k,j}^*). \quad (8)$$

The non-convex unit-modulus constraints in Eq. (7b) form a Riemannian manifold $\mathcal{S}^{ML} = \{\mathbf{f} \in \mathbb{C}^{ML} : |\mathbf{f}(q)| = 1\}$. Hence, (P5) can be iteratively solved via the following steps at each iteration [8]: i) We compute the Riemannian gradient $\mathbf{g} = \nabla f(\mathbf{f}) - \text{Re}\{\nabla f(\mathbf{f}) \odot \mathbf{f}^*\} \odot \mathbf{f}$, where \odot denotes the Hadamard product. ii) By using the RCG algorithm, we update the search direction as $\mathbf{d} = -\mathbf{g} + \alpha \mathcal{T}(\bar{\mathbf{d}})$, where $\mathcal{T}(\mathbf{d}) \triangleq \bar{\mathbf{d}} - \text{Re}\{\mathbf{d} \odot \mathbf{f}^*\} \odot \mathbf{f}$ denotes the vector transport function, α is the Polak-Ribiere conjugate gradient update parameter, and $\bar{\mathbf{d}}$ stands for the previous search direction. iii) We update the RFP via retraction as $\mathbf{f} \leftarrow \frac{(\mathbf{f} + \beta \mathbf{d})_q}{|(\mathbf{f} + \beta \mathbf{d})_q|}$; $\mathbf{F}_R = \text{vec}^{-1}(\mathbf{f})$, where β represents the step size of Armijo backtracking line search. We use the Manopt toolbox (<https://www.manopt.org/index.html>) to implement this algorithm.

3) *Optimizing Θ* : Let us define $b_{k,j} \in \mathbb{C}$ and $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j} \in \mathbb{C}^N$ as $b_{k,j} \triangleq \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j$ and $\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j} \triangleq \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j$, respectively. Then, with all blocks fixed except Θ , problem (P2) is reduced (by ignoring the constant terms) to

$$(P6): \min_{\theta} g(\theta) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} |\theta^\dagger \bar{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j} + b_{k,j} - t_{k,j}|^2 \text{ s.t. C3.} \quad (9)$$

Problem (P6) can be solved by the RCG algorithm, similar to problem (P5). The Euclidean gradient of $g(\theta)$ in problem (P6) over θ is given by

$$\nabla g(\theta) = 2 \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \bar{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j} \left(\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{k,j}^\dagger \theta + b_{k,j}^* - t_{k,j}^* \right). \quad (10)$$

4) *Optimizing $\{\rho_k\}$ and $\{t_{k,j}\}$* : With all variables fixed except $\{\rho_k\}$ and $\{t_{k,j}\}$, problem (P2) is reduced (by ignoring the constant terms) to:

$$(P7): \min_{\{\rho_k\}, \{t_{k,j}\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j - t_{k,j} \right|^2 \text{ s.t. C5-C7.} \quad (11)$$

We initially rearrange the terms in constraint C5, in order to solve problem (P7): C5: $(1 + \gamma_k) |t_{k,k}|^2 \geq \gamma_k \left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} |t_{k,j}|^2 + \sigma_k^2 + \frac{\sigma_{c,k}^2}{\rho_k} \right)$. Then, we define C9: $z_k \geq 0$ as $z_k \triangleq (1 + \gamma_k) |t_{k,k}|^2 - \gamma_k \left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} |t_{k,j}|^2 + \sigma_k^2 \right)$, such that C10: $z_k + \gamma_k \left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} |t_{k,j}|^2 + \sigma_k^2 \right) = (1 + \gamma_k) |t_{k,k}|^2$ and C11: $z_k \rho_k \geq \gamma_k \sigma_{c,k}^2$. Hence, we obtain:

$$(P8): \min_{\{\rho_k\}, \{t_{k,j}\}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j - t_{k,j} \right|^2 \text{ s.t. C6, C7, C9-C11.} \quad (12)$$

Problem (P8) is equivalent to a convex second order cone program (SOCP) formulation and it can be efficiently solved by software tools such as Gurobi (<https://www.gurobi.com/>).

C. Outer-Layer of the Penalty-Based BCD Algorithm

The penalty coefficient δ is initialized at a large value and it is gradually decreased in each iteration of the outer-layer of the proposed algorithm according to $\delta^{(t+1)} = c\delta^{(t)}$, where $0 < c < 1$ is a scaling parameter and t denotes the outer-layer iteration index.

D. Algorithm and Complexity Analysis

The overall algorithm is described in Alg. 1, where ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are predefined thresholds and $\xi \triangleq \max \left\{ \left| \mathbf{h}_k^\dagger \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{f}_j - t_{k,j} \right|^2 \right\}$ denotes the stopping criterion. Note that Alg. 1 is guaranteed to converge and its total complexity is given by $\mathcal{O}(I_O I_I (KL^3 + I_{F_R} K^2 M + I_\Theta K^2 N + K^7))$, where I_O and I_I represent the iteration time of the outer and inner loop, while I_{F_R} and I_Θ correspond to the iteration time of the RCG algorithm for updating the RFP and PB, respectively.

IV. LOW-COMPLEXITY DECOUPLED DESIGN

A. Hybrid Precoder Update

We aim at minimizing the Euclidean distance between the optimal FD precoder (FDP) $\mathbf{W}_* \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times K}$ [1] and the HP $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times K}$, which are defined as $\mathbf{W}_* \triangleq [\mathbf{w}_1^*, \dots, \mathbf{w}_K^*]$ and $\mathbf{F} \triangleq \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{F}_B$ with $\mathbf{w}_k^* \in \mathbb{C}^M$ and $\mathbf{F}_B \triangleq [\mathbf{f}_1, \dots, \mathbf{f}_K] \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times K}$ denoting the corresponding precoding vector assigned to user k and the DBP, respectively:

$$(P9): \min_{\{\mathbf{F}_R, \mathbf{F}_B\}} \|\mathbf{W}_* - \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{F}_B\|_F^2 \text{ s.t. C4.} \quad (13)$$

In order to solve this non-trivial matrix decomposition problem, we apply the AM method. Then, for fixed $\mathbf{F}_R^{(i)}$ at iteration i , (P9) is reduced to an unconstrained least squares problem and $\mathbf{F}_B^{(i)}$ is given by

$$\mathbf{F}_B^{(i)} = \left(\mathbf{F}_R^{(i)} \right)^\dagger \left(\mathbf{F}_R^{(i)} \left(\mathbf{F}_R^{(i)} \right)^\dagger \right)^{-1} \mathbf{W}_*. \quad (14)$$

For given $\mathbf{F}_B^{(i)}$, in turn, (P9) is reduced to:

$$(P10): \mathbf{F}_R^{(i+1)} = \min_{\{\mathbf{F}_R\}} \left\| \mathbf{W}_* - \mathbf{F}_R \mathbf{F}_B^{(i)} \right\|_F^2 \text{ s.t. C4.} \quad (15)$$

(P10) can be solved via manifold optimization, similar to problems (P5) and (P6). However, backtracking line search increases the complexity. Let instead $\mathbf{F}_R \triangleq z(\Phi) \triangleq e^{j\Phi}$, where $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times L}$ represents the analog phase shifts matrix with $\Phi(m, l) = \varphi_{m,l}$. Hence, we form the optimization problem:

$$(P11): \Phi_{i+1} = \arg \min_{\Phi} h(\Phi) = \left\| \mathbf{W}_* - z(\Phi) \mathbf{F}_B^{(i)} \right\|_F^2. \quad (16)$$

Then, we can update the RFP as $\mathbf{F}_R^{(i+1)} = z(\Phi_{i+1})$. Note that $h(\Phi)$ exhibits multiple local minima; thus, standard minimization approaches are not applicable. Nevertheless, this cost function is smooth and its gradient over Φ is given by

$$\nabla h(\Phi) = -2 \text{Re} \left\{ jz(\Phi) \odot a^*(\Phi) \left(\mathbf{F}_B^{(i)} \right)^T \right\}, \quad (17)$$

where $a(\Phi) \triangleq \mathbf{W}_* - z(\Phi) \mathbf{F}_B^{(i)}$.

Next, we apply convolutional smoothing to approximate the cost function in (P11) as a superposition of a uniextremal function and multiextremal ones, with the latter corresponding to the approximation noise. Specifically, at each iteration i , we draw a sample of the probability density function (p.d.f.) $p(\mathbf{S})$, where $\text{vec}(\mathbf{S}) \sim \mathcal{N}(\text{vec}(\mathbf{0}_{M \times L}), c^2 \mathbf{I}_L \otimes b^2 \mathbf{I}_M)$ and

Algorithm 1 Penalty-based Algorithm for Solving (P1).

1: Initialize $\{\mathbf{f}_k\}$, \mathbf{F}_R , Θ , $\{\rho_k\}$, $\{t_{k,j}\}$, and δ ; set $\epsilon_1 > 0$ and $\epsilon_2 > 0$.
2: **repeat**
3: **repeat**
4: Update $\{\mathbf{f}_k\}$ by Eq. (5).
5: Update \mathbf{F}_R by solving (P5).
6: Update Θ by solving (P6).
7: Update $\{\rho_k\}$ and $\{t_{k,j}\}$ by solving (P8).
8: **until**
9: The fractional decrease of the objective value in (P1) is below ϵ_1 .
10: Update δ as $\delta_{\text{new}} = c\delta_{\text{old}}$.
11: **until**
12: The stopping indicator ξ is below ϵ_2 .

$bc = 1$, and then compute the smoothed approximation of the cost function as $h_{\mu_i}(\Phi) = p(\mathbf{S}) * h(\Phi) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{S}}[h(\Phi - \mu_i \mathbf{S})]$, where μ_i denotes a strictly decreasing smoothing sequence. By reducing the amount of smoothing at each iteration, we filter out the approximation noise. Thus, instead of trying to minimize $h(\Phi)$, we seek to solve in each iteration the stochastic optimization task (P12): $\min_{\Phi} h_{\mu_i}(\Phi)$. To solve problem (P12), we employ the SGD algorithm. That is, we compute the two-sided gradient estimate of $h_{\mu_i}(\Phi_i^{(t)})$ as $\nabla h_{\mu_i}(\Phi_i^{(t)}) = \nabla h(\Phi_i^{(t)} + \mu_i \mathbf{S}) + \nabla h(\Phi_i^{(t)} - \mu_i \mathbf{S})$ according to Eq. (17), where t is the iteration index of the SGD algorithm, and then we update the analog phase shifts matrix as $\Phi_i^{(t+1)} = \Phi_i^{(t)} - \eta \nabla h_{\mu_i}(\Phi_i^{(t)})$, where $\eta > 0$ is the SGD update step. After convergence, we set $\Phi_{i+1} = \Phi_i^{(t+1)}$.

B. Power Splitting Ratios Update

To obtain ρ_k^* , we solve the FDP optimization problem for fixed Θ in [1] with fixed $\mathbf{w}_k = \mathbf{F}_R^* \mathbf{f}_k^*$, $\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$. This is a convex feasibility-check problem that can be efficiently solved by software tools such as CVX (<http://cvxr.com/cvx>).

C. Passive Beamformer Update

For given HP and PS ratios, the transmit sum-power minimization problem is reduced to a feasibility-check problem:

$$(P13): \text{Find } \theta \text{ s.t. C1–C3.} \quad (18)$$

Let us define $\mathbf{b}_{k,j} \in \mathbb{C}^N$, $\Psi_{k,j} \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N} \times \bar{N}}$, $\bar{\theta} \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N}}$, and $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{C}^{\bar{N} \times \bar{N}}$ as $\mathbf{b}_{k,j} \triangleq \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{F}_R^* \mathbf{f}_j^*$, $\Psi_{k,j} \triangleq [\mathbf{b}_{k,j} \mathbf{b}_{k,j}^\dagger, \mathbf{b}_{k,j} \mathbf{b}_{k,j}^*; \mathbf{b}_{k,j}^\dagger \mathbf{b}_{k,j}, 0]$, $\bar{\theta} \triangleq [\theta; 1]$, and $\mathbf{V} \triangleq \bar{\theta} \bar{\theta}^\dagger$, where $\bar{N} \triangleq N + 1$. Then, (P13) is converted to:

$$(P14): \text{Find } \mathbf{V} \quad (19a)$$

$$\text{s.t. C12: } \text{Tr}(\Psi_{k,k} \mathbf{V}) + |b_{k,k}|^2 \geq$$

$$\Gamma_k \left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{K} \setminus \{k\}} \left(\text{Tr}(\Psi_{k,j} \mathbf{V}) + |b_{k,j}|^2 \right) \right), \quad (19b)$$

$$\text{C13: } \sum_{j \in \mathcal{K}} \left(\text{Tr}(\Psi_{k,j} \mathbf{V}) + |b_{k,j}|^2 \right) \geq \frac{Q_k}{(1 - \rho_k)}, \quad (19c)$$

$$\text{C14: } \mathbf{V}(n, n) = 1, \quad n = 1, \dots, \bar{N}; \quad \text{C15: } \mathbf{V} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \quad (19d)$$

Algorithm 2 Optimization Algorithm for Decoupled Design.

1: Initialize $\{\mathbf{f}_k\}$, \mathbf{F}_R , Θ , and $\{\rho_k\}$, $\{t_{k,j}\}$; set $\epsilon_3 > 0$ and $\epsilon_4 > 0$.
2: **repeat**
3: Update $\{\mathbf{f}_k\}$ by Eq. (14).
4: Update \mathbf{F}_R by solving (P12).
5: **until**
6: The fractional decrease of the objective value in (P9) is below ϵ_3 .
7: Update $\{\rho_k\}$ by solving the FDP optimization problem for fixed Θ and $\mathbf{w}_k = \mathbf{F}_R^* \mathbf{f}_k^*$.
8: **repeat**
9: Update Θ by solving (P15).
10: **until**
11: The fractional decrease of the objective value in (P15) is below ϵ_4 .

$$\text{C16: Rank}(\mathbf{V}) = 1. \quad (19e)$$

Since the semi-definite relaxation of (P14) is not tight [9] and Gaussian randomization does not guarantee convergence, we approximate instead the non-convex rank constraint C16 as C17: $\|\mathbf{V}\|_* - \|\mathbf{V}\|_2 \leq 0$, where $\|\mathbf{V}\|_* = \sum_n \sigma_n(\mathbf{V}) \geq \|\mathbf{V}\|_2 = \max_n \{\sigma_n(\mathbf{V})\}$ and $\sigma_n(\mathbf{V})$ denotes the n -th singular value of \mathbf{V} . The equality in C17 holds if and only if \mathbf{V} is rank-one. Thus, we drop C16 from problem (P14) and seek to minimize $\|\mathbf{V}\|_* - \|\mathbf{V}\|_2$. However, the resulting problem is non-convex, since the considered cost function consists of the difference of convex (D.C.) functions. We address this issue by applying the SCA method. Specifically, for any feasible point $\mathbf{V}^{(r)}$, we have $\|\mathbf{V}\|_2 \geq \|\mathbf{V}^{(r)}\|_2 + \text{Tr} \left(\mathbf{v}_{\max}^{(r)} \left(\mathbf{v}_{\max}^{(r)} \right)^\dagger (\mathbf{V} - \mathbf{V}^{(r)}) \right) \triangleq \bar{V}^{(r)}$, where $\mathbf{v}_{\max}^{(r)}$ is the eigenvector that corresponds to the maximum eigenvalue of $\mathbf{V}^{(r)}$ and r denotes the iteration index. Hence, we obtain the implicit feasibility problem (P15), which is convex and can be solved in polynomial time by CVX:

$$(P15): \min_{\mathbf{V}} \|\mathbf{V}\|_* - \bar{V}^{(r)} \text{ s.t. C12–C15.} \quad (20)$$

D. Algorithm and Complexity Analysis

In Alg. 2, ϵ_3 and ϵ_4 are predefined thresholds. The worst-case complexity of the AM algorithm for computing the HP is given by $\mathcal{O}(ML^2 |\mathcal{S}| T_{\max})$, where $|\mathcal{S}|$ denotes the length of the smoothing sequence and T_{\max} is the maximum number of iterations. The approximate complexity of (P15) in each iteration is $\mathcal{O}(\bar{N})$.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we comparatively evaluate the performance of the proposed designs against benchmarks via numerical simulation results. It is assumed that $K = 2$, $M = 24$, and $\sigma_k^2 = \sigma^2 = -70$ dBm, $\sigma_{c,k}^2 = \sigma_c^2 = -50$ dBm, and $\bar{Q}_k = \bar{Q} = -15$ dBm, $\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$. We adopt the non-linear logistic EH model used in [10] with saturation threshold $P_{\text{sat}} = 13.8$ dBm and parameters $\bar{a} = 150$ and $\bar{b} = 0.024$. We also apply the correlated Rayleigh fading channel model [11] with path loss exponent set to 2.5. The results are averages obtained after 100 independent channel realizations generated in Matlab (<https://www.mathworks.com/products/matlab.html>).

Fig. 2. (a) Transmit sum-power vs. SINR threshold. (b) Transmit sum-power vs. number of IRS elements.

The considered schemes are the joint FDP/PB/PS design [4], the proposed joint and decoupled HP/PB/PS designs (with RFP updates in the latter case based on either the SGD or the RCG algorithm), and a heuristic decoupled HP/PB/PS design where the RFP is computed based on the singular value decomposition (SVD) of the composite matrix of effective channels [3]. We also consider scenarios where random IRS phase shifts are utilized or no IRS is deployed.

Fig. 3 illustrates the transmit sum-power vs. varying SINR threshold $\gamma_k = \gamma = 2.5 : 2.5 : 10$ dB, $\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$, for different number of RF chains $L = 6 : 2 : 10$, assuming $N = 256$. In Fig. 4 is depicted the transmit sum-power vs. a varying number of IRS elements $N = 64 : 64 : 256$, assuming $\gamma_k = \gamma = 0$ dB and $L = 6$. We observe that: 1) The proposed designs perform better than the joint FDP/PB/PS design. 2) The joint HP/PB/PS design outperforms the respective decoupled ones. Among these decoupled design variants, the RCG-based scheme performs better than the SGD-based one. 3) The SVD-based decoupled design presents the worst performance, since the RFP computation is not optimization-based, but instead it relies on a heuristic. 4) Higher SINR thresholds and larger number of RF chains result in higher transmit sum-power. 5) The use of an IRS substantially improves the performance. The transmit sum-power is reduced with the number of the IRS elements. Even when a random PB is utilized, there is some performance gain in comparison to the case where no IRS is deployed. However, in this scenario, the system is less sensitive in the increase of the number of IRS elements. Also, there is a large performance gap with respect to the case where the PB is optimized, since when a random PB is employed the IRS does not exploit the channel knowledge.

VI. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposed the combination of IRS-aided multi-user MISO communication with hybrid precoding for

energy-efficient SWIPT and presented a corresponding joint HP/PB/PS design as well as respective low-complexity decoupled designs. Numerical simulations demonstrated that by exploiting the direct channel and leveraging a large number of IRS elements, we can achieve significant performance gains.

REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Shi, L. Liu, W. Xu, and R. Zhang, "Joint Transmit Beamforming and Receive Power Splitting for MISO SWIPT Systems," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 3269–3280, Jun. 2014.
- [2] A. Li and C. Masouros, "Energy-Efficient SWIPT: From Fully Digital to Hybrid Analog–Digital Beamforming," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 3390–3405, Apr. 2018.
- [3] K. Ntougias, I. Krikidis, G. K. Papageorgiou, and M. Sellathurai, "Hybrid Precoding for MISO Broadcasting SWIPT Systems: A Stochastic Optimization Approach," in *IEEE Annu. Int. Symp. Pers. Indoor Mobile Radio Commun. (PIMRC)*, London, UK, Sep. 2020.
- [4] Q. Wu and R. Zhang, "Joint Active and Passive Beamforming Optimization for Intelligent Reflecting Surface Assisted SWIPT under QoS Constraints," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 38, no. 8, pp. 1735–1748, Aug. 2020.
- [5] B. Guo, R. Li, and M. Tao, "Joint Design of Hybrid Beamforming and Phase Shifts in RIS-Aided mmWave Communication Systems," in *IEEE Wireless Commun. Netw. Conf. (WCNC)*, Nanjing, China, Mar. 2021.
- [6] W. Hao *et al.*, "Robust Design for Intelligent Reflecting Surface-Assisted MIMO-OFDMA Terahertz IoT Networks," *IEEE Internet of Things J. (IIOT)*, vol. 8, no. 16, pp. 13 052–13 064, Aug. 2021.
- [7] J. Xue, X. Zhou, C. Wang, D. Wang, Y. Zhao, and Z. Li, "Hybrid Precoding for IRS-assisted Secure mmWave Communication System with SWIPT," in *Int. Conf. Space-Air-Ground Comput. (SAGC)*, Beijing, China, Dec. 2020.
- [8] P.-A. Absil, R. Mahony, and R. Sepulchre, *Optimization Algorithms on Matrix Manifolds*. Princeton University Press, 2009.
- [9] Q. Wu and R. Zhang, "Intelligent Reflecting Surface Enhanced Wireless Network via Joint Active and Passive Beamforming," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 18, no. 11, pp. 5394–5409, Nov. 2019.
- [10] Y. Lu, K. Xiong, J. Liu, P. Fan, and Z. Zhong, "Optimal Coordinated Beamforming with Artificial Noise for Secure SWIPT in Multi-Cell Networks," *EURASIP J. Wireless Commun. Netw.*, no. 60, Mar. 2018.
- [11] M.-M. Zhao, Q. Wu, M.-J. Zhao, and R. Zhang, "Intelligent Reflecting Surface Enhanced Wireless Networks: Two-Timescale Beamforming Optimization," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 2–17, Jan. 2021.